

Ancient Narratives, Modern Echoes: The Study of Deception, Identity, and Ethics in Manipuri Folktales

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Abstract

This research paper examines the impact of traditional Manipuri folktales on contemporary ethical challenges related to deception, identity, and the ethical use of information. The selected folktales are “The Witch Without Chin”, “The Demon Queen,” and “Yenkha Paodabi” (The Eavesdropper). They provide valuable perspectives on human behavior and social norms relevant to today’s digital age. The analysis demonstrates that these folktales offer significant lessons for understanding and responding to the digital world. This research reaffirms the significance of folklore in providing moral guidance. It also emphasizes the role of traditional narratives in fostering a culture of integrity and transparency in contemporary society.

Keywords: Deception, Digital age, Ethical dilemmas, Folktales, Identity

Introduction

Folklore is that part of a people’s culture which is preserved, consciously or unconsciously, in beliefs and practices, customs and observances of general currency; in myths, legends, and tales of common acceptance; and in arts and crafts which express the temper and genius of a group rather than of an individual. Because it is a repository of popular traditions and an integral element of the popular “climate,” folklore serves as a constant source and frame of reference for more formal literature and art; but it is distinct therefrom in that it is essentially of the people, by the people, and for the people.” (Gaster, 399) Oral history, which is composed of customs from a particular people’s culture, is reflected in folklore. It describes a popula-

tion’s values, beliefs, and preferred way of life through various themes. A folktale is a genre of folklore in which the story was originally passed down from one generation to the next, and its origin is unknown. It is narrated by the elderly members of the family. Despite having different versions of a single tale over the ages, the themes remain unchanged. According to Stith Thompson, “Of all the folklore, it is the folktale that holds the most significance for the serious student of literature” (874). The folktales’ plots are straightforward, but these may be analyzed and examined from various angles, including structural and comparative analysis, anthropological viewpoints, psychology, etc. It is an important socialization strategy that can captivate the minds of the future generation and uplift the culture and traditions of a community. Manipur, a state in northeast India, is home to a diverse ethnic group, with a long history of traditions and cultures. The state has a valley where the Meitei people predominate and hills surrounding the valley where the inhabitants are tribal. They have unique cultures, dialects, histories, religions, etc. Folktales are referred to as “Funga-wari” in Manipuri, where funga means “furnace” and wari means “story.” Children used to gather around the kitchen furnace to listen to folktales narrated by their grandparents. Manipuri folktales can be categorized as animal tales, human tales, magical tales, jokes, tales of deceit, and proverb tales. This research paper analyses the impact of traditional folktales on today’s ethical challenges regarding deception, identity, and the ethical use of information. The study draws on three narratives, “The Witch Without Chin,” “The Demon Queen,” and “Yenkha Paodabi” which provide a significant understanding of human behavior and social norms that are relevant to the issues in today’s digital age. Folktales are integral to cultural transmission, conveying complex societal values and ethics through engaging and

memorable narratives. They play a key role in the moral education of communities, embodying societies' collective wisdom and ethical challenges. The impact of these stories is their flexibility to adapt to different contexts, making them relevant across various times by emphasizing universal human experiences and moral issues.

Objectives

The objective of this research is to explore selected Manipuri folktales relating to deception, identity, and the ethical use of information. Folktales have long served as repositories of cultural wisdom, offering moral lessons that transcend time and continue to be relevant in different historical and technological contexts. This study seeks to demonstrate that the narratives of "The Witch Without Chin," "The Demon Queen," and "Yenkha Paodabi" are not just relics of the past but remain significant in addressing modern concerns. By analyzing these folktales, the research aims to establish how traditional storytelling can illuminate critical issues such as digital deception, identity manipulation, and data privacy breaches. The study also endeavors to show how folktales, as a form of cultural transmission, play a vital role in shaping ethical perspectives, fostering moral discourse, and guiding decision-making in a rapidly evolving digital society.

Methodology

The research methodology adopted in this study is primarily qualitative, drawing on narrative analysis and comparative examination. The study relies on textual analysis to deconstruct the themes and moral lessons embedded in the selected Manipuri folktales. By interpreting these narratives through the lens of contemporary ethical issues, the research bridges the gap between oral traditions and modern dilemmas. The methodology also includes a comparative approach, juxtaposing the folktales against real-world scenarios in which deception, identity theft, and ethical misuse of information manifest in digital spaces. In addition, scholarly

works on folklore, cultural studies, and digital ethics are referenced to support the arguments and provide a broader theoretical framework. Secondary sources, including academic papers, books, and online repositories, are utilized to contextualize the folktales within both their traditional setting and their modern relevance. The analysis involves identifying key motifs, character behaviors, and narrative structures that parallel contemporary ethical concerns, thus demonstrating the enduring applicability of these folktales.

The Witch Without Chin

This folktale is about a hardworking husband and his lazy, greedy wife. While the husband toils to provide for the family, the wife secretly eats all the delicious food alone and deceives her husband by blaming a mythical "witch without a chin" for the missing food. Suspecting her of deception, the husband pretends to leave for a trip but secretly watches her prepare and feast on the best food. Catching her red-handed, he exposes her, calling her the "witch without a chin." Ashamed, the wife flees to her maiden home. The story highlights the consequences of greed and dishonesty.

Veiled Betrayals: Folklore's Mirror on Modern Misinformation

"The Witch Without Chin" is a metaphor for the wider effects of deceit in modern society. With the rise of misinformation and deception, particularly in digital media and communications, the tale highlights the dangers of dishonesty and its ability to erode trust in close relationships. It portrays a hardworking husband who endeavors to provide for his family, while his wife avoids her household duties and hides the best portions of the meal, he brings home for herself. She manipulates the truth to cover up the disappearance of the meal she made, pursuing personal gain at the expense of others' hardships. This can be related to today's society where individuals may fabricate the truth and present false personas online and in personal interactions to gain social, emotional, and financial benefits. The disappearance of the meal and the fictional witch illustrates how lies can entangle the deceiver and the de-

ceived in mistrust. The confrontation between a husband and wife in which he expresses suspicions of infidelity represents a serious moment in their relationship. It can permanently destroy the trust they have in each other. This scenario is not uncommon in real-life situations where one partner discovers the deception of the other, resulting in emotional pain and often, the termination of the relationship. In contemporary contexts, it can be observed in relationships affected by online affairs, financial debt, or prior incidents shared on social media. The strategy of ascribing blame to an imaginary chinless witch for the missing food reflects society's proclivity to shift responsibility and construct narratives that deflect from one's transgressions. The proliferation of false information, or "fake news," has led to a pervasive skepticism among the public. This is because misinformation is often employed strategically to deceive individuals, thereby underscoring the importance of fostering a culture of honesty and open communication. By doing so, individuals can mitigate the impact of false information and avoid the negative consequences of deceit. In this folktale, a couple's failure to establish open dialogue led to the propagation of deceit. Promoting honesty and clarity helps people clear misunderstandings and reduces the chances of deceit. "The Witch Without Chin" demonstrates the ongoing struggle between truth and deception in society, where information can enlighten or manipulate.

The Demon Queen

The folktale follows a widowed king who unknowingly marries a demoness disguised as a beautiful woman. She pretends to love his two young princes but secretly plans to have them eaten by her mother, an old demoness. Tricking the king, she takes the princes to the forest, leaving them with her mother. The clever princes win the old demoness' trust while secretly gathering different magical leaves that can cause floods, summoning leeches, and the third

creating fire. When they escape, the demon queen's mother chases them, but they use the magical leaves to defeat her. Returning home, they expose the demoness queen, who then reveals her true form but is swiftly killed by the king's soldiers. The king, choosing not to remarry, lives happily with his brave sons.

Shadows and Thrones: Folklore's Relevance to Contemporary Dilemmas

"The Demon Queen" explores themes of deception, manipulation, and resilience, which are highly relevant to today's social issues. The grieving King, who had lost his wife, was lured by a demon disguised as a beautiful damsel. She managed to become Queen while hiding her true intent of murdering two young princes. This symbolizes contemporary issues of identity deception, trust in interpersonal relationships, and psychological manipulation. The tale illustrates the complexities between identity manipulation and the usurpation of power within a royal family. The demon's transformation into a beautiful woman is not merely physical but includes a deeply calculated emotional strategy designed to gain trust and infiltrate the royal household. This physical deception is like how some individuals present themselves on social media. It may be to appeal to specific audiences and to fit societal standards. The demon's method also displays modern phenomena such as catfishing. Some people create false identities online to forge emotional connections with unsuspecting victims. Like the demon, in this folktale, catfishers often fabricate entire personas completely with false stories and emotional cues designed to elicit sympathy, trust, and admiration. The implications of the demon's actions also outline the damage that modern identity fraud can inflict on individuals and communities. Her position as a queen threatens the royal family and the entire kingdom. Her disguise and the ultimate motive to devour the princes undermine the foundation of trust upon which personal, professional, and civic relationships are built. Additionally, the demon's desire to harm the royal family and the repercussions of her deception can extend beyond the immediate targets. In today's

world, identity theft can lead to serious consequences such as conflicts among family members. This is because stolen assets or false debts can break a relationship and cause irreparable damage. Moreover, it can also lead to a loss of trust within the community. People may become more cautious and distrustful in their interactions, fearing that they may be taken advantage of. In the digital world, anonymity and distance make it easier for fraudsters to manipulate and exploit people. The Demon Queen” signals the need for vigilance and protective measures against those who exploit emotional and social connections for harmful purposes. The demon is a stepmother to the princes who secretly resent them. This vulnerability holds particular significance in foster care and adoption scenarios where children are placed in new family environments. Some children may encounter situations where their emotional and physical safety is compromised by those entrusted with their care. It is not unusual for caregivers to fail in their duty to protect, guide, and nurture. The folktale also presents the importance of resilience and coping strategies in adverse conditions. The young princes’ adept use of knowledge and resources to secure their survival symbolically shows the role of empowerment through education and awareness, particularly in contexts where people face abuse and manipulation.

Yenkha Paodabi (The Eavesdropper)

This folktale is about a couple who unknowingly become the target of a cunning demon, Yenkha Paodabi Saigung Pollibi. The demon takes advantage of a simple riddle game to plot her scheme, disguising herself as the wife to deceive the husband. However, when the real wife returns, chaos ensues as both claim to be the true wife. Unable to determine the truth, the villagers take the case to the wise king, who devises a clever test using a hollow bamboo pipe, claiming that only the real wife can pass

through it. The overconfident demon falls into the trap, revealing her identity. Instead of punishing her with death, the king shows mercy, ensuring justice is served. The tale highlights the importance of intelligence, righteousness, and the triumph of truth over deceit.

Echoes of Deception: A Folkloric Perspective on Identity and Privacy Challenges

“Yenkha Paodabi” also explores themes of deception, identity confusion, and the mechanisms societies use to determine truth. It bridges the mythological and the mundane and resonates with contemporary issues such as identity verification and privacy breaches. The story revolves around a demon who eavesdrops on a couple and uses the information to impersonate one of them. This infiltration highlights the dual nature of information access in our digital era, where data can be empowered and exploited. The demon’s impersonation raises questions about the essence of identity and how it is authenticated, which parallels modern cybersecurity and data protection challenges. The folktale also illustrates how eavesdropping violates personal spaces and privacies, like unauthorized surveillance and data mining. The struggle to identify the true wife mirrors contemporary efforts to verify identity and authenticate truth, highlighting the reliance on technology and jurisprudence. The folktale provides a narrative framework to question and refine our understanding of how personal identity is constructed, protected, and authenticated in an increasingly interconnected world. The act of deception in this folktale aligns with modern concerns about privacy violations and the misuse of personal data. Cybercriminals and fraudsters use similar methods in contemporary society and often turn to social engineering to manipulate individuals into revealing personal information, passwords, or financial details. These actions are motivated by financial gain or malicious intent, similar to the demon’s blend of malevolence and strategic deceit. The demon is motivated by sinister desires to associate with and harm the human community. Cybercriminals have various motivations. Some aim for profit

through financial fraud or identity theft, while others are driven by ideological reasons, such as spreading misinformation or causing societal disharmony. The demon's act of impersonation creates confusion and conflicts within the community. This highlights how deceit can diminish the trust upon which relationships are built. It is harmful because it not only affects the immediate victims but also has a ripple effect through the community, showing doubt, and insecurity. Today, truthful information is crucial. Misinformation and deceit on digital platforms can sway political outcomes and incite unrest. The challenge is maintaining transparency and accountability in a world where deception can be anonymous and widespread. Nowadays, with advanced technology, it has become increasingly easy for cybercriminals to steal personal data and create fake identities. This tale emphasizes the critical need for robust verification processes in various sectors, especially in banking, healthcare, and legal systems, where identifying individuals accurately is crucial. However, it also explains the potential inadequacy of these mechanisms. Current technologies and protocols often limit modern verification systems, enabling sophisticated fraudsters to bypass them. The husband and the villagers struggle in the folktale to identify the real wife. These challenges parallel those encountered by modern verification systems. In the story, eavesdropping leads to events that ultimately cause an identity crisis. This act is similar to the contemporary issues of digital surveillance, where personal information can be monitored and accessed without consent or knowledge. The tale questions how privacy is protected and respected, and the balance between necessary surveillance for security purposes and the right to personal privacy. In contemporary society, the abundance of digital footprints and the ease of access and analysis pose significant challenges. Ethical concerns arise from how data is collected, stored, and used, and whether individuals whose

information is being handled are aware and have consented to these processes. Just as the community in the folktale must decide how to react to the deceit exposed among them, modern society must navigate the complexities of data privacy and surveillance in technology-driven interactions. The story shows us that privacy protections need to be updated as technology changes. Apart from the laws and technologies, it is necessary to be aware of the new threats and changes in the digital world.

Findings

One of the major findings in this research is that deception, identity, and ethical dilemmas have profound implications for the modern digital landscape. Moreover, it underscores the importance of honesty and transparency in both traditional and digital communication, where trust remains a crucial factor. The study also finds that deception is used to manipulate emotions and gain power. This resonates with modern anxieties about identity theft, social media manipulation, and the consequences of false representation in digital and social contexts. Additionally, it also addresses privacy violations and the misuse of sensitive information, an issue that has become increasingly prevalent in the era of digital surveillance, data breaches, and unethical data collection practices. The study concludes that the moral lessons embedded in these folktales are not only historically significant but also highly applicable to contemporary society. By revisiting and analyzing these narratives, individuals can gain valuable insights into ethical behavior, critical thinking, and the importance of safeguarding personal integrity in an interconnected world. Ultimately, this research affirms that folklore, far from being an obsolete cultural artifact, continues to serve as a powerful lens through which contemporary ethical challenges can be examined and understood.

Conclusion

The analysis of "The Witch Without Chin," "The Demon Queen," and "Yenkha Paodabi" observes the persistent relevance of folktales in illuminating modern

issues of deception, identity, and the ethical use of information. The lessons in such tales can be studied and related to societal problems. In a society increasingly dominated by digital communication, the tales serve as a cautionary reminder of the importance of sincerity and integrity. They also present the complexities of identity deception and the profound impacts of such fraudulence on individuals and communities. The tale is a metaphor for the potential dangers lurking behind seemingly benign profiles in our interconnected digital world, emphasizing the need for vigilance and critical assessment of online interactions. Drawing from these narratives, it becomes evident that while the platforms and contexts might have evolved, the core human concerns around trust, truth, and deception remain unchanged. These stories are impressions of the collective responsibility to foster a culture of honesty and transparency. They urge the audience to strengthen legal frameworks to safeguard against deceit and manipulation. Moreover, these tales underscore the importance of resilience and adaptability. Just as the characters in the stories often overcome deceit through wisdom and perseverance, modern societies adopt strategies to cope with and mitigate the impacts of deceit and misinformation. Education and awareness are crucial in empowering individuals to discern truth from falsehood and protect themselves from the potential threat of others. The analysis observes the persistent relevance of folktales in illuminating modern issues of deception, identity, and the ethical use of information. The lessons in such tales can be studied and related to societal problems. In a society increasingly dominated by digital communication, the tales serve as a cautionary reminder of the importance of sincerity and integrity. They also present the complexities of identity deception and the profound impacts of such fraudulence on individuals and communities. The tale is a metaphor for the potential dangers lurking behind seemingly benign profiles in the interconnected digital world, emphasizing the need for vigilance and critical assessment of online interac-

tions. To conclude, the analysis of these folktales observes the perennial themes of human behavior showing specific pathways through which contemporary society can address the ethical dilemmas posed by modern technology.

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